

Solar parks could become significant carbon stores

Active grassland management with organic fertiliser, sheep grazing and seeding could increase the amount of carbon stored in grassland soils

Policy context and recommendations

- Land use change and land management are well known to alter land carbon emissions. However, little is understood of the effects of land use change for solar parks, a rapidly growing new land use, on soil carbon sequestration.
- Post-Brexit agricultural policies are likely to pay landowners for land carbon sequestration, and a UK Farm Soil Carbon Code is being developed to channel private investment in practices that sequester carbon in soil. It is therefore critical to understand which grassland management practices commonly used at solar parks – seeding, mowing, grazing, nutrient addition – could be applied to increase soil carbon sequestration.
- Soil carbon response to these management practices is highly variable, but those most likely to result in soil carbon sequestration within UK solar parks include organic nutrient addition (slurry and biosolids), low to moderate intensity sheep grazing, seeding of diverse plant communities and legume planting.
- Removal of vegetation cover and long-term mineral fertilisation within solar parks should be discouraged as they are more likely to result in grassland soil carbon loss over time.
- Standardised monitoring is needed to ensure active land management within solar parks is delivering soil carbon gains, especially in light of the uncertain evidence. Robust scientific evidence could feed into future policy development, as well as inform industry practice and future industry accreditation schemes.

Challenge

Which grassland management practices have the greatest potential to ensure UK solar parks can sequester as much carbon as possible? We answer this question by reviewing existing scientific evidence of vegetation management effects on grassland soil carbon to identify appropriate land management practices that could enhance soil carbon sequestration in solar parks.

Method

Common grassland management techniques applicable to UK solar parks were identified as plant diversity manipulation, mowing, grazing and nutrient addition. Evidence of the effects of these vegetation management practices on grassland soil carbon in the UK and Ireland was extracted from academic databases (Academic Search Ultimate, GreenFILE and Web of Science) in April 2020 following published review guidelines (Pullin & Stewart, 2006, *Conservation Biology*, 20:1647-56). Pre-defined eligibility criteria were detailed in a systematic review [protocol](#) registered with the Open Science Framework in April 2020. The relevant evidence meeting the eligibility criteria was classified according to the effects of land management on grassland soil carbon and categorised as soil carbon loss, no change in soil carbon or soil carbon gain as a direct result of the management intervention in question. Statistical hypothesis testing was applied to determine whether the evidence count between these three outcomes were evenly distributed or biased towards one particular outcome.

Results

- Evidence stemmed from 60 peer-reviewed academic journal articles published between 1989 and 2020, reporting 155 individual lines of evidence distributed between loss, no change or gain in soil carbon as a result of the three types of vegetation management found in the literature, including plant diversity manipulation, grazing and nutrient addition (Figure 1).
- Nutrient addition accounted for most of the evidence (76.8%), followed by grazing (16.8%) and plant diversity manipulation (6.4%).

- No evidence on the effects of mowing on grassland soil carbon was found.
- The statistical analysis showed that:
 1. Nutrient addition was mostly associated with no change in soil carbon.
 2. Soil carbon response to grazing was equally distributed between loss, no change and gain in soil carbon.
 3. There was insufficient evidence from plant diversity manipulation studies to perform statistical testing, but this type of management showed a slight trend towards no change in soil carbon.
- Organic nutrient addition (eg slurry, biosolids) and low to moderate intensity sheep grazing were identified as the most likely practices to result in grassland soil carbon gains.
- Liming and urea applications were also likely to result in soil carbon gains over time.
- Seeding diverse plant communities and swapping mineral fertilisers for legume addition have also been found to enhance soil carbon accrual in grasslands.
- The removal of vegetation cover (ie resulting in bare soil) and long-term mineral fertilisation were the most likely practices to result in soil carbon loss.

Figure 1 Counts of evidence attributed to soil carbon loss, no change or soil carbon gain (see legend at the top) as a result of different types of vegetation management, including plant diversity manipulation, grazing and nutrient addition.

Find out more

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Further project information and a detailed review methodology can be found here: <https://osf.io/gxtm5>

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